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D3.1 “Manuscript for paper or report on theory advances/test on diagonalization of operator through coordinate transformation D3.1

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable D3.1, "Manuscript for Paper or Report on Theory Advances/Test on Diagonalization of Operator through Coordinate Transformation " has the aim of establishing an appropriate theoretical basis for the definition of a generalized sorter that would allow for the recognition of the protein without making a full image it.

We called this process *diagonalization*, since the image of the protein should result in an abstract set of pixels, like a diagonal matrix. The aforementioned problem is very difficult for proteins that typically produce a small phase change. In fact it can be demonstrated impossible with a simple unitary change of basis. Here we try to tackle it by adopting different approaches developed by the theory groups working on Q-SORT, and we propose a range of possible solutions. The current document is structured as a report to improve its readability, however most of the approaches hereby presented are mature enough to become 4 or 5 manuscripts that will be submitted through the appropriate channels/journals for publication.

Chapter 1 presents the problem of diagonalization in more mathematical terms with 2 different formulations and desired features for the solution.

Sections 2 to 6 present 5 different solutions based on 1) numerical optimization (Sect 2); 2) phase compensation in an OAM sorter spectrum (sect 3); 3) optical computational ghost images (sect 4-6) with different effective phase scrambler.

More specifically, chapter 2 describes the solution where we use of a direct numerical approach to produce two phase elements in direct and Fourier planes that transform each target beam in a nearly point-like diffraction.

Chapter 3 illustrates the solution where we add a third phase element to a conventional OAM sorter to compensate the phase and obtain a sparse further diffraction

Chapter 4 presents the use of random caustic pattern to sample the protein in a single pixel imaging scheme

Chapter 5 is devoted to the use of many orders of aberration purposely introduced in the microscope pattern to sample the protein in a single pixel imaging scheme

Chapter 6 is proposes to the use a linear channel like a fiber and a time of flight revelation to sample the protein

Chapter 7 summarizes the results and outlines the strategies for the future phase elements to be nanofabricated as priorities.

This deliverable is related to the activity carried out in the following tasks:

Task 3.1: General theory for coordinate transformation and wavefunction superposition for the diagonalization of arbitrary (protein specific) measurements (methods and limits)

Task 3.2: Optical bench testing of new measurement procedure and diagonalization.

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This deliverable is also linked to the milestone *MS4. Specification of requirement of protein specific
sorter*. This will be discussed briefly in the conclusions

1 GENERAL FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

The effect of the protein on the beam is mainly a phase effect: Given $V(x,y)$ namely the z-averaged electrostatic potential of the atoms the effect of the protein is mainly:

$$\psi_{ew}(x, y) = A(x, y)\exp(i\sigma V(x, y))\psi_{probe}(x, y) \quad (1)$$

Where σ is a coupling constant and A is a small amplitude effect, $\psi_{probe}(x, y)$ is the probe before the sample. $\psi_{probe}(x, y)$ in normal TEM is a plane wave but we can modify it in the sorting process.

When there is no protein (Vacuum), the wave function has just $A=1$, $\phi = 0$. On the contrary A is nearly constant because typically proteins are based on light atoms.

Fig 1 amplitude and phase of the wave after scattering through a protein.

The protein amplitude A and phase $\phi = \sigma V(x, y)$ in the most symmetric direction of the “protein hepta *pdbid 3J83*” looks like fig 1.

It has also to be noted that the phase effect is also quite small as $\phi = \sigma V(x, y) \ll 2\pi$

It is easy to demonstrate that for every weak phase object, if we define the pointwise scalar product as

$$\psi \cdot \phi = \int \psi^* \phi d\vec{r} \quad (2)$$

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the wavefunction ψ_{ew} for a protein is not orthogonal to the vacuum. This has important consequences on the feasibility of the protein sorter as shown in section 1.4

In the following paragraphs, we define in rigorous mathematical terms the problem of the sorting for proteins.

We want the representation of the protein after the transform onto appear sparse namely made of very few points after the change of basis and ideally with only one peak.

The idea is that if the relevant information is concentrated in few points even few electrons can be sufficient to win over background noise with an evident advantage in terms of dose.

Mathematically, this sparsity can be described by the 2 formulations below.

1.1 Strong formulation

We want to find a unitary transformation U such that the wavefunction ψ_{ew} becomes

- 1) $\delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_1)$ when the protein is in the beam
- 2) $\delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_0)$ or very diffused if there is no protein.

This requirement regards a single protein in a single orientation and is therefore the minimal requirement. It would be best if this could be extended to many different proteins and protein orientations.

1.2 Weak formulation

We want to find a unitary transformation U such that the wavefunction ψ_{ew} after it becomes sparse, namely

- 1) $U\psi_{ew} = \sum_i^n C_i \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_i)$ on the protein (with n quite small)
- 2) $U\psi_{ew}$ whatever on the protein but very different from 1

This is the minimal requirement. It would be best if this could be extended to many different protein directions.

1.3 Request for the rotation/translation invariance

It would be highly desirable that an in-plane rotation (and a translation) in the protein would not produce a change in the sorting since they are equivalent for the work of recognizing the protein. It is indeed clear that the random in plane orientation is an information of no importance in the project. The in 3D orientation is instead relevant.

We can relax this condition by allowing for the rotation to be accounted for by a phase or additionally if the weak formulation is used a small intensity redistribution among the sparse coefficient C_i .

Two examples of success cases are the following:

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- 1) The normal Fraunhofer Diffraction gives an intensity pattern that is independent of the translation
- 2) The OAM sorter gives an OAM spectrum, in it the rotation is absorbed in the phase of the OAM peaks.

Considering point 2 it would be interesting to build on the OAM sorter.

1.4 Feasibility

The scalar product is defined in (1). As already mentioned according to this product the ψ_{ew} for vacuum (plane wave) and for the protein are not-orthogonal. This fact is true for all pairs of functions with nonzero amplitude and whose phase difference never reach π .

$$\text{Max}(\arg(\psi_{ew1} / \psi_{ew0})) < \pi$$

This condition often applies to our protein.

A unitary transformation preserves the scalar product, this means that it is impossible to sort proteins according to the requests of the "Strong formulation" because it would take non-orthogonal states into orthogonal ones (delta is automatically orthogonal). Unless a non-unitary transformation is used.

OAM sorting, for example, is a unitary transformation.

1.5 Additional desired features

For the practical realization on the TEM a number of further desired properties are here described :

- 1) It would be nice if, in addition to the basic requirements (as in 1.1 and 1.2), we would be able to distinguish two or more proteins or more 3D orientations of the same protein.
- 2) The number of phase elements to produce the transformation were limited to 3 since 3 is the number of aperture available in the microscope
- 3) The phase effects could be produced with essentially harmonic phase structures, namely $\nabla_{x,y}\varphi = 0$ *almost everywhere*, since these can be produced with a limited number of electrodes

1.6 Matrix formulation

Numerically ψ_{ew} is a x,y matrix or image (assumed here square) of n x n complex wave values.

However, ψ_{ew} could be also rewritten as a single array $N = n \times n$, this can be done for example by tiling all the matrix rows consecutively.

In this case the U is the N x N namely much larger than the size of the wavefunction.

In a sense this already is a hint that it is impossible to produce the general transformation U for all cases, but we must limit the number of requests for the ψ_{ew} set that need to be distinguished/sorted.

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Of course, a possible solution is to renounce to the general transformation and to aim to a restricted solution for a finite number m of proteins to be identified.

If we imagine that the proteins are sampled on $n \times n$, the phase plates must be sampled on a $n \times n \times m$ points. In a single pixel of the protein, we encode different sorting. It is obvious to expect an m dependent loss of intensity.

2 SOLUTION 1: DIRECT NUMERICAL OPTIMIZATION

Numerical methods have been studied that permit to optimize the two-phase elements in two opposite planes (direct and reciprocal plane) as form of generalization of the OAM sorter [1]. The algorithm change the two-phase elements until the aimed objects are transformed to isolated peaks in the new basis.

In detail we developed a numerical technique to design holograms that transform wavefunction superpositions in their eigenmodes constituents. The numerical methods are based on genetic algorithms and Fourier analysis. The optimization is performed by considering a set of input modes incident on a first phase hologram. A subsequent quadratic phase term, simulating a focusing operation, was additionally imprinted. The light field then undergoes free-space propagation until it reaches the second phase hologram. Due to the lens-term, the field is now close to the Fourier-plane, i.e. far field. After imprinting the second phase element followed by another quadratic phase term, the field is propagated further until it reaches the final plane where sorting is achieved. Pixel by pixel, the phase holograms are made to vary in order to optimize the simultaneous sorting at the output plane of a given number of modes at the input plane. To reduce unwanted scattering process due to very strong phase gradient and the restrictions mentioned above (1.5), we blurred both phase elements using a Gaussian-Filter during the optimization procedure.

To test the algorithm we used a set of orthogonal states, namely the Laguerre Gaussian, states here indicated by the (l,p) notation for the azimuthal and radial quantum number.

Numerically we tested a specific numerical optimization, the holograms that sorts azimuthal and radial modes are shown below for a set of 6 modes, i.e. $(l,p) = (0,0), (1,0), (-1,0), (0,1), (1,1)$ and $(-1,1)$

The relevant modes and the holograms found after the optimization are shown in figure 2. Figure 3 shows the resulting final diffraction as well as a cross-talk matrix. Using such methods yields an efficiency that scales with $1/N$, where N is given by the number of modes that is sorted.

Fig 2 Tested Laguerre Gauss mode set and examples of optimized phase mask to be used to sort LG modes

Fig 3 Calculated diffraction after the second phase mask for the modes $(l,p) = (0,0), (1,0), (-1,0), (0,1), (1,1)$ and $(-1,1)$ and the measured cross-talk matrix. A cross talk of maximally 10% is found.

A first attempt at experimentally implementing the genetic algorithm methods to generate the sorting holograms directly in the laboratory is shown in fig 4. A diode laser at a wavelength of 810 nm was employed. A total of 3 spatial light modulators (SLM) was necessary to perform sorting. The first SLM (SLM1), which has a resolution of 600 pixels by 800 pixels, was used in order to generate the modes. An intensity masking technique was considered in order to simultaneously manipulate the intensity and the phase of the input modes. The second SLM (SLM2), which also has a resolution of 600 pixels by 800 pixels, was used to generate the first phase element. Similar to the simulation, an additional lens was added on the phase element on the SLM. The focal length of the lens was made to match with the distance between SLM2 and SLM3, where SLM3 corresponded to the second phase element. Another lens was added at the SLM3 with the focal length matching with the distance between SLM3 and a CCD camera. Images were recorded from the CCD camera and used as a feedback for the real-time genetic algorithm. From the measured intensity scans, a new set of holograms are displayed on SLM2 and SLM3. This process was repeated until the point where an optimal sorting of the input modes was achieved given the experimental configuration.

Experimental results for three input modes, $l=-1,0$ and 1 , are shown below.

Fig 4 Experimental realization in an optics bench for $l=-1,0$ and 1

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This method can be applied to orthogonal states and still need to be improved to deal with the case of the protein. For this case an appropriate orthogonal state decomposition must be found such that its representation is mainly sparse.

1. G.C. G. Berkhout et al Phys. Rev. Lett. 105, 153601 (2018)

3 SOLUTION 2: GENERALIZATION BASE ON OAM SORTER

In the solution we discuss the possibility of identifying the organic macromolecule, such as the protein in figure 1a), by means of OAM modes decomposition in a 3 elements electron sorter.

Fig 5 image of the protein in cartesian (a) and polar (b) coordinates and relative diffraction

For this preliminary discussion, we assume we can have a perfect OAM sorter. As a first step, the phase of the protein is transformed into log polar coordinates (figure 5b) and then Fourier transposed (figure 1c). This result is equivalent at passing the electron probe after the interaction with the molecule into an ideal OAM sorter, which does not introduce any distortion or artifact. In this case the molecule doesn't have any well-defined azimuthal symmetry therefore no evident features appear in the OAM decomposition.

However, every vertical stripe in image 5c correspond to a single OAM component. If we select and isolate a single stripe (figure 5a and 5b), in this case $l=6$, back Fourier transform it and then retransfer it in Cartesian coordinates, we obtain the single OAM component of the image (figure 5c)

Fig 6 (a) selection of a single L channel, phase image of the single L channel in OAM spectrum and in real Cartesian coordinate real space

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As it can be noted, the swirling phase in figure 5c contains a distinctive radial component that is characteristic, and therefore can be used to identify, the molecule under illumination. The radial component of the phase is encoded in the vertical stripe shown in figure 5b.

In the following we will use a third phase element and a cylindrical lens after the plane of the OAM spectrum so as to reach diffraction in the vertical direction (corresponding to the radial degree of freedom) while keeping the OAM in the spectrum plane.

It naturally follows that such third phase element in the sorter can be used to match and neutralize the radial component of the phase for each OAM component separately. A perfectly phase matched element would produce a very narrow diffraction in the final plane

The phase of such a sorter is reported in figure 6.

Fig 7 Phase mask to be applied on the single channel for phase compensation

Once the phase has been neutralized, the 1D Fourier transformation will focalize the entire stripe's intensity in a single point on the optical axis, as shown in figure 6a and 6b where the generalized sorter is applied on the $l=6$ component of the molecule.

Of course, because the third component is protein specific, it will not work for any other molecule as demonstrated in figure 8 and 9.

Fig 8 shows the full 2D spectrum for the proteins in 2 orientations after a phase compensation for a single channel. The first protein shows a clear peak in the red rectangle region that is not present for

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the second protein orientation. Therefore, even on a single OAM channel we are able to distinguish the 2 cases.

Fig 9 is a more drastic example where the protein specific phase element 3 is added to each OAM channel. The transformed spectrum is very localized. In particular we show that with a dose as low as

$1e / \text{\AA}^2$ the two protein images are well distinguished.

Note that:

- 1) Such a compressed spectrum is independent of any rotation of the molecule since this adds only a constant phase factor at each OAM channel
- 2) Even if the protein produces a small phase change, the phase of the spectrum wave has a strong phase signature spanning the range $0-2\pi$. This is because the protein is obtained as the sum of strong phase orthogonal eigenfunction.

Fig 8 Example of recognition of OAM-radial momentum for 2 protein orientations

Fig 9 Example of application of the protein recognition to two orientations. If the right protein is introduced in the log-polar spectrum appears its characteristic form with a limited dose (b,c) even as low as $1e/\text{Å}^2$. However, if the wrong protein or orientation is introduced (d) the spectrum appears featureless.

4. SOLUTION 3: SINGLE-PIXEL IMAGING USING CAUSTIC PATTERNS

In this solution we use an un conventional imaging idea to shift the problem of the imaging of proteins from the imaging system to the programmable phase plate preparation. It is difficult at the moment to evaluate the advantage in terms of dose.

4.1. Abstract

We show that a sequence of projected caustic intensity patterns can be used as the basis for the single-pixel imaging of objects. Since caustic patterns are a natural consequence of random phase masks the principle can be applied to a wide range of wavelengths and wave types and various implementations phase masks. For example, the caustics are formed by the refraction of light by ocean waves and hence could be used to perform imaging of submerged objects.

4.2 Optics realization

Single-pixel cameras are a form of computational imaging where a time-varying mask is used to create projected patterns to illuminate an object alongside a single-pixel detector to measure the total time-varying intensity of the backscattered light. Equivalently the object can be illuminated full field and the time varying mask be inserted prior to the detector. In both configurations, the signals from the detector are a measure of the overlap between the mask pattern with the object and given many such measurements corresponding to different patterns it is possible to reconstruct the object [1]. The potential advantage of such approaches is that they negate the need for detector arrays, which can be prohibitively expensive at some operating wavelengths.

Much of the research in the area of single-pixels cameras has been directed towards the choice/design of mask patterns and the algorithms needed to reconstruct the image from the mask and detector data. The choice of patterns range from those based upon random laser speckle [2], to those implemented using spatial light modulators including both Hadamard [3] and more bespoke patterns aimed at optimizing specific scenarios [4], computer addressable, spatial light modulators capable of creating complicated masks at very high refresh rates. This need for spatial light modulators itself sets limitation upon the operating wavelengths requiring sophisticated solutions at any wavelength much removed from the visible spectrum [5].

The selection of speckle patters as the illumination obviously makes possible the use of a wide variety of random processes for their generation, but still leaves the problem of needing to know the precise spatial form of the pattern produced. Recording the pattern often requires a detector array to do so and hence negates the technological advantage of the approach. In this work we consider, as an alternative to speckle, the use of caustic patterns that are for generated whenever light is reflected or transmitted through a slowly varying phase mask (for example the patterns formed on the bottom of a swimming pool, resulting from the imperfect focusing of the sunlight by the ripples on the surface of the water). In general when a slowly varying phase mask is illuminated with a coherent light source then although speckle is obtained in the far field, the near field produces caustics, and the transition between the two has been studied previously [6]. Using caustics for ghost imaging has been considered previously but

in that case did not yield experimental results [7]. In this present work we perform proof of principle single-pixel imaging using caustic patterns, which although we demonstrate using a programmable spatial light modulator could be implemented by other systems at other wavelengths.

Fig. 10: Experimental realization. The output from a HeNe laser is magnified and spatially filtered using a **50mm** focal length lens (L1), a **50µm** precision pin-hole (A) and a **150mm** focal length lens (L2). A Cambridge Correlators liquid-crystals SLM is used to impart the caustics hologram onto the incoming collimated beam. The first diffracted order is selected by an aperture (not-shown in the diagram) placed in the far-field of a **300mm** focal length lens (L3). A **600mm** focal length lens (L4) is used in conjunction to L3 to magnify the caustics pattern. A beam-splitter (BS) is used to divert 50% of the incoming light to a spatially resolved detector (camera). An object (Obj.) and the camera are placed at a determined distance beyond the image plane of the SLM. A ground-glass plate (GGP) placed immediately after the object is used to diffuse the light transmitted through the object, ensuring that the light reaching by the photo-multiplier tube single-pixel detector arose from all regions of the object equally alike, thus avoiding partial measurement of the object and a bright spot on the optical axis.

As shown in the experimental arrangement in Fig. 0, the output beam from a He Ne laser is collimated and expanded to fill the aperture of a spatial light modulator. This modulator is programmed to display a random phase mask, but one that is fully within the $0 - 2\pi$ range. The scale of these phase fluctuations is such that the light is approximately locally focused a few $100mm$ after the plane of the modulator (c.f. the floor of a swimming pool). To ensure the fidelity of the phase fluctuations, the modulator is used in diffractive mode where the additional of a phase grating to the phase mask produces the desired complex beam in the first diffractive order which is selected in the far-field of the modulator and then re-imaged to create a virtual modular at some other plane. The object is then placed at the required distance after this virtual plane. The overlap between the object and the caustic pattern is measured in transmission using a larger area photomultiplier. Knowledge of the spatial form of the projected caustic pattern can be acquired from a direct measurement with a camera positioned in the caustic plane or modelled from knowledge of the phase mask using a plane-wave decomposition. The random phase mask is calculated by assigning every pixel a random value and

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then applying a spatial low-pass filter to obtain a slowly varying random pattern which can then be rescaled to lie in the $0 - 2\pi$ range.

Fig. shows examples of the phase masks applied (a), the corresponding hologram displayed on the SLM (b), and the caustic pattern as measured by the CCD (c).

Fig. 11: Caustics are generated using a spatial light modulator. A phase mask (a) is used to generate a hologram (b) that is displayed on the SLM. The resulting intensity pattern of the caustics is recorded by the CCD (c).

Using a sequence of these random caustic patterns to illuminate the object and measuring the single-pixel signal allows the image to be reconstructed. If the caustic patterns are described by p_i and the measured overlap signals are ms_i then a traditional reconstruction algorithm for the image I_N from N mask patterns is given by $I_N = \sum_{i=1}^N (ms_i - \langle ms \rangle) \cdot p_i$ where $\langle ms \rangle$ denotes the average value of all available overlap signals [8,9].

Fig. 1212 shows the reconstructed image of a Siemens star resolution target. As anticipated we see that the reconstructed image based on measured caustic patterns is highly similar to that based on the modelled patterns predicted from knowledge of the generating phase mask.

Fig. 12: Reconstructed image of a Siemens star resolution target. The image of an eight-spokes resolution target (a) was reconstructed using the modelled caustics intensity patterns and signals (b) and the experimentally measured caustics and signals (c).

An interesting feature of these reconstructed images is that the low spatial frequencies are poorly reproduced, and this is reflective upon the near absence of low spatial frequencies in the power spectrum of the caustic patterns and is visible in the reconstructed image shown in 13 (b). The object used is shown in Fig. 13 (a).

Fig. 13: Reconstructed image of an object using caustic patterns. The reconstructed image appears to be edge-enhanced, as a result of missing low-spatial frequencies in the used caustic patterns. This image was reconstructed using $\approx 14,000$ caustic patterns.

The nature of caustic formation is that it is lensless and hence has no uniquely specific plane. It can be shown that the range is not critical albeit in all cases the resolution of the resulting image falls below that which would have been obtained from a diffraction limited system.

In this work we have shown that a sequence of projected caustic intensity patterns can be used as the basis for single-pixel imaging of objects. Since caustic patterns are a natural consequence of random phase masks the principle can be applied to a wide range of possible wavelengths and wave types

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and various implementations of phase masks. For example, the caustics are formed by the refraction of light by ocean waves and hence could be used to perform imaging of submerged objects.

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5. SOLUTION 4: RECONSTRUCTION THROUGH VARIABLE ABERRATION IMAGING

This solution is particularly appealing because the programmable phase is obtained directly by the aberration of the microscope controlled by the aberration corrector without losing electron. It would be also possible to use two sets of electrodes to produce an equivalent but handier version of the corrector.

As before, we cannot quantify yet the advantages of this ghost imaging approach in comparison with the amount of dose necessary for imaging.

5.1 Abstract

One form of computational imaging relies upon a projected sequence of different illumination patterns and a measurement of the backscattered light associated with each to reconstruct an image estimate of the unknown object. The frequently cited advantage of such an approach is that the detector array that would normally be placed in the image plane of the camera can be substituted with a single element (pixel) detector and hence access wavelengths where detector arrays are either unobtainable or very costly. This form of computational imaging based on sequences of projected pattern sequences is called a “single-pixel camera” or “computational ghost imager”. What we show in this work is that by appropriate choice of illumination patterns the resolution of the reconstructed image can exceed the diffraction limit. Specifically, rather than compensating for aberrations, we introduce time varying aberrations in the form of Zernike polynomials to create complicated point spread functions with super oscillatory spatial features and it is these features that allow us to recover spatial information beyond the diffraction limit. Compared to a simple, aberration-free imaging system based on a scanning a diffraction-limited spot, we show that by deliberately introducing excess aberrations we can double the lateral resolution. Such a technique is applicable to any imaging system based upon projected light where the aberrations are understood and controllable and could for example be implemented using spatial light modulators, deformable mirrors or even potentially with electron beams using aberration control.

5.2 Optics realisation

Single-pixel cameras use a programmable mask to either project an illumination pattern or filter the backscattered light to measure the overlap between the mask pattern and the object scene [1]. This overlap is measured using a single element (pixel) detector large enough to integrate over the entire field of view. By employing a known sequence of masks, it is possible to reconstruct an estimate of the entire image. The potential of this approach lies in two aspects, firstly that single-pixel detector is available at wavelengths where the detector arrays for normal cameras are not [2]. Secondly, that by appropriate choice of masks and prior assumptions about image properties then the number of masks required to obtain a good estimate of the image can be far fewer than the number of pixels in the image – a example of compressed sensing.

The choice of mask patterns is central to the performance of the system and the required algorithms used to reconstruct the image. One popular choice are masks derived from Hadamard matrices where each mask probes a subset of spatial frequencies. These masks are orthogonal which simplifies the

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reconstruction algorithm that can be as simple the additional of all the mask pattern used, each weighted by the magnitude of the overlap signal recorded by the single-pixel detector. If the mask patterns are orthogonal with respect to each other then the number of masks and corresponding required is exactly equal to the number of pixels in the image. However, if one is willing to apply constraints to the reconstruction, e.g. that the image is sparse in its spatial frequencies then, as stated above, it is possible to reconstruct a high-quality measurement from a significantly smaller number of mask patterns and measurements.

If the mask patterns are implemented using a pixelated spatial light modulator then specifying their design to be orthogonal is straightforward (e.g. Hadamard, or similar). If, however, the patterns are produced in other ways, e.g. using natural scattering, then orthogonality between the patterns can no longer be enforced and the reconstruction algorithm becomes more complicated. One approach to solving this non-orthogonality relies upon traditional Matrix inversion, but since the size of the matrix is very large (number of elements \approx number of pixels²) then this inversion is, at best, computationally intensive and more generally difficult to constrain based upon assumptions about the image. Here we report an alternative approach that is computationally trivial and hence updateable on a pattern by pattern.

If the patterns are described by p_i and the measured overlap signals are ms_i then a traditional reconstruction algorithm for the image I_N from N mask patterns are given by[3,4]

$$I_N = \sum_{i=1}^N (ms_i - \langle ms \rangle) p_i. \quad (1)$$

We call this algorithm “traditional ghost imaging, (TGI)”

If the patterns are not orthogonal then this algorithm fails since the non-orthogonal components, i.e. overlapping parts of p_i , are overly emphasized in the image reconstruction.

An alternative algorithm can be devised which iterates towards an image reconstruction based on the current estimate modified by the new pattern and signal. Key to this algorithm the ability to predict the signal that would be obtained from any pattern under the assumption that the previously calculated image was complete. This predicted signal, based on an image estimate I_j , is given as $ps(I_j)$. The iterative reconstruction of the image from a sequence of applied patterns is then given as

$$I_i = I_{i-1} + [(ms_i - \langle ms \rangle) - (ps(I_{i-1}) - \langle ps \rangle)] p_i, \#(2)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes the average value and $I_0 = 0$.

We call this algorithm “orthogonalized ghost imaging, (OGI).”

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Note that care needs to be taken such that both the measured and predicted are correctly scaled such that as the reconstructed images approaches the true image that the quantity $[(ms_i - \langle ms \rangle) - (ps_{(I_{i-1})} - \langle ps \rangle)]$ tends to zero. One approach to ensuring this scaling is to iteratively normalize the signals such that $\langle ps \rangle = \langle ms \rangle$ and $\sigma_{ps} = \sigma_{ms}$.

In this work we adopt a random weighting of Zernike polynomials, to produce random aberration and hence a sequence of highly distorted point spread functions in the far field. Using the first four orders of Zernike polynomials (tip/tilt, astigmatism/defocus, trefoil/coma and quatrefoil/secondary astigmatism/spherical aberration), see figure 14, multiplied to give several wavelengths of aberration we can calculate the far-field point spread functions, see figure 15.

Fig. 14 - The 14 the lowest order Zernike polynomials, depicted in terms of their phase profile where the grey scale ranges denotes $0-2\pi$. (first row, tip/tilt; second row, astigmatism/defocus, third row, trefoil/coma and fourth row, quatrefoil/secondary astigmatism/spherical aberration).

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We take these calculated point spread functions as the pattern sequence, p_i with which to illuminate the object and then model the backscattered signal in terms of the correlation between the pattern and the object, which we take as the measured signal, s_i . We then take these modelled signals and calculated the anticipated reconstructed image as obtain from equation 1 and equation 2.

For the purpose of our numerical model we assume a 4mm diameter beam illuminating a 10mm sized spatial light modulator, programmed to apply the random aberrations. The aberrated beam is then

propagated using plane-wave decomposition to a focusing lens of 2m focal length with the test object placed in the back focal plane of this lens. The backscattered signal is calculated as being in proportion to the overlap between this object and the aberrated beam.

Fig. 15 - Random combinations of Zernike aberrations (top) and the corresponding calculated far-field point spread functions (bottom).

Fig. 16 - Reconstruction based upon 10,000 patterns like those in figure 2 using both the TGI and OGI algorithms, calculated on a 512x512 array.

Figure 16 shows the reconstructed images obtained after 10,000 Zernike aberration patterns using both traditional and orthogonal ghost imaging reconstruction algorithms. By analysing the depth of the reconstructed intensity modulation as a function of radius from the centre (normalised to the peak modulation) figure 4 shows that the resolution of the OGI images is approximately twice that of the TGI image. We note also that the corrective nature of the algorithm has also flattened the modulation transfer function to give a more equal response to a wider range of spatial frequencies.

Fig. 17 - The intensity modulation depth as a function of radius for images obtained using 10,000 Zernike random aberrations and reconstructed using both TGI and OGI.

Rather than comparing TGI to OGI a more interesting comparison can be made to the images that can be obtained by simply removing all aberrations other than tip/tilt, to give a randomly scanning diffraction limited spot. Figure 5 shows the reconstructed images obtained after 10,000 randomly positioned diffraction-limited spots using both traditional and orthogonal ghost imaging reconstruction algorithms. By analysing the depth of the reconstructed intensity modulation as a function of radius from the centre (normalized to the peak modulation) figure 17 shows that the resolution of the OGI images is equivalent to that of the TGI image. More significantly neither of the reconstruction algorithms using data acquired from the scanning spot match the resolution of the image produced using OGI using the patterns derived from the Zernike aberrations.

Fig. 18 - Reconstructions based upon 10,000 randomly positioned diffraction limited spots using both the TGI and OGI algorithms, calculated on a 512x512 array.

Fig. 19 - The intensity modulation depth as a function of radius for images obtained using 10,000 randomly position diffraction limited spots, reconstructed using both TGI and OGI.

These results seem to indicate that a computational imaging system based upon the projection of a sequence of randomly derived, but known, heavy aberrated spots can improve upon the diffraction limited image that could have been obtained from a scanning, diffraction-limited but none aberrated spots. The physical origin of this improvement lies in the super oscillatory spatial features of the aberrated point spread functions

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6. SOLUTION 5: USING A LINEAR CHANNEL

We mention here optical studies that use an optical fiber to form computational images. The actual implementation in the microscope could be again some system of phase plates with random phase. Therefore, we will actively work on creating a set of 2 electrodes phase plates that produces the appropriate imaging. This work also relies on time of flight but for the moment this seems to be beyond the reach in an electron microscope.

6.1 Abstract

Imaging through scattering media has recently gone from the realm of fiction to reality with the advent of high speed wave front shaping using spatial light modulators and digital micromirror devices. This has made it possible to measure the full transmission matrix of a multimode fibre in a reasonable time frame. Early implementations of this system are showing very promising results as extremely small endoscopes. However, retrieving images of objects in the far field of the fibres has proven more of a challenge. Here we use a sub-ns pulsed laser to not only retrieve 2D images from the far field of a multimode fibre, but we also record the time of flight to add depth of information and produce 3D images of scenes up to a meter beyond the far end of a fiber.

6.2 Realization

Scattering media, e.g. fog, turbulent liquids, ground glass, etc., have always been a hurdle for imaging. Their very nature scrambles the information content in transmitted light, leading to a degradation of the quality of any image we try to retrieve from beyond. Crucially though, in most cases the light is scrambled, but not lost. This makes this a computationally challenging problem, but not a fundamentally insurmountable one.

With the increase in available computing power this problem has been approached in a number of ways in recent years. From the very early work in astronomy using guide stars, to more recent work relying on machine learning to recover images from sparse data[1]. One method that in particular gives high quality results for strongly scattering systems relies on the ability to measure that systems response to a large number of inputs, thereby constructing a transmission matrix (TM) for the system that describes the propagation of light from input to output[2,3]. For most scattering systems the number of available transmission modes in the medium are far higher than can be sampled in a reasonable time frame, but a finite number of sampled modes already allows for reasonable reconstructions of images[4]. The TM method is made possible through the use of high-speed beam shaping methods that quickly allow the addressing of different modes and the combinations thereof. Originally this was achieved with spatial light modulators (SLMs), though more recently digital micromirror devices (DMDs) have become the instrument of choice because of their significantly higher switching speeds while retaining fidelity[5].

One type of system that fits the transmission matrix method perfectly is the multimode fibre (MMF). MMFs are highly efficient at guiding a finite number of propagating modes, but effectively opaque for all other modes. Their transmission matrix can therefore be fully described by a fixed and manageable

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number of modes, typically in the range of a few thousand, well within the range of our current computational ability. At the same time the different propagation constants of these modes in the fibre lead to a very strong scrambling of input light, which closely resembles the effects of highly scattering media, strongly influenced by specific conditions such as bending of the fibre, temperature or stresses[4].

It has previously been shown that applying the transmission matrix method to the imaging problem in the case of multimode fibres leads to very promising results[3,4]. In general the aim is to employ fibres as microendoscopy tools. Moreover, the objects being imaged would remain close to the fibre distal end, which mitigates the effect of the small aperture on the light collection ability of the system.

In this paper we attempt to extend the use of the transmission matrix method of imaging through multimode fibres to the far field at the distal end, retrieving images from up to a meter away. Moreover, we achieve this using a sub-ns pulsed laser source which allows us to also recover temporal information of the scene and thus recover not only 2D, but rudimentary 3D images with an axial resolution of approximately 5cm.

The primary source of the scrambling of light propagating through multimode fibres is not scattering, but modal dispersion[6]. Put simply, light can only propagate through the fibre in a fixed set of modes determined by the fibre core diameter and the refractive index difference between core and cladding, the latter of which can be summarized by the numerical aperture (NA) of the fibre. Each of these modes has a slightly different value of k_z , the axial component of the wavevector, and therefore acquires a different phase upon propagation from one end of the fibre to the other. Most of the scrambling therefore stems solely from the decomposition of an input light field into a subsection of these modes, which then quickly develop a chaotic set of phase differences and therefore collectively form a speckle interference pattern. A secondary contribution to the scrambling stems from the coupling between neighboring modes due to the MMF typically not being a perfect cylinder, which becomes a more or less significant factor depending on how severely perturbed the fibre is.

This modal dispersion-based scrambling is one of the reasons why the TM method works so well for MMFs, but it also exacerbates a problem. Namely that the set of possible modes is dependent on the frequency of the light, and therefore a measured TM is only valid for a very specific frequency. Most of the work in the field is therefore done with very narrow line width, or long coherence length, lasers. However, as we want to include time of flight in our measurements we require the use of a pulsed laser, which necessarily restricts the coherence length. In other words, there is a trade-off between the length of the MMF and the achievable resolution of the time of flight. For a single TM to be valid for all modes they all need to be able to interfere with a high degree of visibility at the distal end, i.e. their optical path lengths need to be sufficiently similar.

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To determine a minimal condition where this is true, it suffices to look at the optical path length difference between the shortest and longest possible optical path lengths, or the lowest and highest order fibre modes[3]. These can be approximated geometrically as

$$z_{low} = nL, \#(1)$$

and

$$z_{high} = \frac{nL}{\cos\left(\sin^{-1}\left(\frac{NA}{n}\right)\right)} = \frac{z_{low}}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{NA}{n}\right)^2}}, \#(2)$$

where n is the refractive index of the fibre core, L is the physical length of the fibre, and NA the numerical aperture.

Fig 20– Schematic of the experimental setup. f_1 (120mm lens), a_1 (30 μ m aperture) and f_2 (300mm lens) form a spatial filter and beam expander to illuminate the DMD with an \sim 1cm diameter collimated Gaussian beam at 24° from the normal. The brightest diffraction order is then converted to circular polarisation by a linear polariser and quarter waveplate. f_3 (400mm lens) is placed at f after the DMD in that arm, with a_2 (iris) placed in the Fourier plane to filter out only the first order. f_4 (80mm lens) and f_5 (40x objective) act as a telescope to project this plane onto the input facet of MMF1 (50 μ m core, 0.22 NA, 20cm long, fc/pc coupled patch cable.) The other end of the multimode fibre is aimed at a screen \sim 15cm away for the characterization step, or a general scene for the imaging. The camera images this screen for the characterisation, with both it and the DMD triggered by pd_1 , a reference

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photodiode directly after the laser. During imaging the reflected light is instead sampled by MMF2
(500 μm core,

0.22 NA, 20cm long, SMA coupled patch cable), the other end of which is put into direct contact with a
fast APD (Avalanche Photodiode) with a square detector area of 500 μm on a side. The signal from
this APD is fed into a high-speed digitizer, along with a reference signal from pd2 (high speed
photodiode) which is placed just after a3 (iris) in the Fourier plane of the DMD in the corresponding
negative diffraction arm.

The difference between these values, Δz , should be far shorter than the coherence length, L_{coh} , of the
laser to allow for good control of the output interference effects, or visibility, at the end of the fibre.

For a pulsed laser this coherence length can be written as:

$$L_{coh} = c\Delta t/n, \#(3)$$

where c is the speed of light in vacuum and Δt the pulse length. Combining the above leaves

Fig. 21 - Pictures of the far field intensity after a multimode fibre. a) Speckle formed due to a spot
focused on the input facet. b) Spot produced after correcting for the fibre TM.

$$\Delta z = nL \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{NA}{n}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) \ll L_{coh} = \frac{c\Delta t}{n}. \#(4)$$

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For a typical multimode fibre with NA of ~ 0.22 and refractive index ~ 1.45 , this reduces to approximately $L \ll 40c\Delta t$. To be safe we required a visibility of 0.999, which equates to the length of the fibre needing

to be less than approximately the coherence length of the laser in free space. To satisfy this we chose to use a 20cm long fibre with a numerical aperture of 0.22 alongside a 0.67ns pulse length Q-switched laser with a center wavelength of $0.532\mu\text{m}$, which corresponds to a coherence length in free space of $\sim 20\text{cm}$.

Achieving imaging through multimode fibres with the transmission matrix method requires several steps. The first of which is measuring the actual transmission matrix. We mostly follow the plane wave method with an internal reference as previously described by Tomas Cizmar's group[5]. The experimental setup used is illustrated in figure 20. This method involves placing a digital micromirror device (DMD) in a Fourier plane of the input facet of an MMF, suitably magnified to make optimal use of the full face of the

DMD. The fibre is then characterized by scanning a regular grid of angled plane waves at the DMD, i.e. a set of linear gratings with varying k_x and k_y , which then form an array of focal spots at the fibre facet. At any one time a superposition of two such plane waves are displayed, one of which is kept fixed as the internal reference throughout the characterization step. At the same time the resultant speckle pattern at the output of the fibre is imaged, an example of which is shown in figure 21a. By varying the phase of the internal reference for each sample plane wave this method allows the retrieval of both the amplitude and the phase contribution to the TM from that sample plane wave for each spatial coordinate on the camera.

This method was chosen for experimental convenience, not necessarily because it gives the best possible results. The primary advantages of using an internal reference over an external arm are ease of alignment, as the path lengths of reference and sample are essentially identical and there is no need for extra access to the output end of the fibre with a secondary light path. The main disadvantage is that the reference is now a speckle pattern with unknown spatial phase distribution, which leads both to the phase relationship between different rows of the measured TM to be ambiguous as well as to areas of very low intensity in the reference where the TM cannot be accurately measured. Similarly the primary advantage of using a plane wave basis at the DMD is an increase in the efficiency of the use of laser power during the characterization procedure, as most of the DMD face is active for every measurement, while the alternative subdomain approach also discussed in [5] uses less than a 1000th of the DMD at any one time. The disadvantage is that processing the resulting TM into useful holograms for imaging is far more computationally intensive in this basis.

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The main difference between our implementation of the characterization and the previous work is the plane at which the resultant speckle patterns are imaged. Rather than imaging the output facet directly, we instead let the light naturally propagate approximately 15cm after the fibre. We then image the speckle pattern as visible on a white scattering screen. This method was chosen as it immediately includes the propagation into the far field in the measured transmission matrix, removing the need of computationally doing so. As this is easily in the far field of the fibre, the speckle pattern beyond this point uniformly scales as it diverges, but does not otherwise significantly develop further. Therefore, a single transmission matrix is valid for the entire range of distances we're interested in if measured in this

fashion. This does however drastically reduce the peak intensity of the measured speckle patterns during characterization, due to the power being distributed over a $\sim 7.5\text{cm}$ diameter circle rather than the $50\mu\text{m}$ core of the fiber facet.

The transmission matrix we find in this manner is incomplete, as the relative phase information between spatial points at the output, or rows in the TM, is left ambiguous.

Fig 22 - Calibration measurements for the time of flight. a) Subset of the measured temporal histograms recovered when positioning a screen at various distances beyond the fibre. The maxima of the peaks as indicated fall off with approximately $1/t^2$. b) Temporal positions of the peaks in the measured histograms against the physical distance of the screen beyond the fibre. The line is a fit with the expected slope of $c/2$, i.e. the speed of light and a correction for the return trip of the pulses.

Full control over the output field is therefore not possible, but the formation of a single focal spot beyond the fibre is, with an example shown in figure 21b. This is done by coherently summing the plane waves at the DMD offset with the phase of a row of the TM, which ensures constructive interference between all contributions at the corresponding output spot. While the peak power of the resulting spots can be almost three orders of magnitude higher than the average background intensity, this still leaves a significant background speckle, with the power in the focal spot accounting for approximately a third of the total power. 2D imaging can then be accomplished in a straightforward fashion akin to single pixel imaging techniques, namely by scanning an array of such spots sequentially across a target scene and recording the total reflected power to the fibre from each point

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to reconstruct an image. 3D information is added by measuring not only the total reflected power, but also a histogram of the time of arrival of the returning light, which maps to the distance from the fibre in the direction of the focal spot.

As shown in figure 22, for our current implementation the reflected light is collected by a second multimode fibre placed in close proximity to the illumination fibre, rather than doing both with the same fibre. This second fibre has a core diameter of $500\mu\text{m}$ with the same NA as the illumination fibre and is coupled directly to an avalanche photo diode to act as a bulk detection aperture. We chose this approach for the prove of concept of 3D imaging, as it avoids problems with detection cross talk with light reflected directly at the fibre facets that arises when using a single multimode fibre for both illumination and detection. This seemed prudent given the extremely low signal that makes it back to the MMFs when used to image scenes significantly further away from the fibres than the core diameter, or aperture size. We note however, that in principle the pulsed nature of the light used here should make it possible to time gate the returning signal to filter out the undesired components.

The time of flight is measured with respect to a trigger signal measured by a reference detector placed in the path of the opposite diffraction order to the one used to probe the actual fibre. This ensures that the detector is only triggered when the DMD is being used to scan the scene, which facilitates the synchronization between illuminated patterns and detected signals. The distance from the fibre as a function of time is then calibrated with a single focal spot displayed in the center of the field of view, reflected off the same white screen used for the TM measurement at a variety of distances. The results of this measurement are shown in figure 23.

Fig. 23 - Example of scene imaged beyond multimode fibre. a) Scene being imaged, the snowman is at approximately 50cm beyond the fibre, the dinosaur at 60cm. b) 3D projection of the retrieved image. c) Intensity in z-plane corresponding to position of the snowman. d) Intensity in the z-plane corresponding to the dinosaur.

An example of an image retrieved by the described system is shown in figure 23. The APD's analogue signal is converted to a discretized histogram of intensities against time by a high-speed digitizer operating at 2.5GHz, or 0.4ns per bin, which gives a corresponding axial resolution of 6cm. The histograms and pixel map together form an image cube, which can either be visualized as individual 2D images at different distances as in figure 23c and 23d, or used to extract a 3D image using the locations of the maxima of the histograms as the corresponding z coordinate as in figure 4b. As our spots still come with a significant background speckle intensity, we subtract the average of all histograms from each histogram before finding the maxima.

The lateral resolution of these images is limited by the number of fibre modes[7]; in the sense that the size of the focal spots diverges with the same NA as fibre, or in other words the number of diffraction limited spots in the field of view, $N = \frac{d^2}{(\lambda/2NA)^2}$, where d is the diameter of the fibre core, doesn't change with distance from the fibre. The field of view meanwhile increases with a divergence angle set by the

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fibre NA, i.e. $A = \pi \left(\tan(\sin^{-1}(NA)) \cdot z + \frac{d}{2} \right)^2 \approx \pi(NA \cdot z)^2$, in the paraxial approximation with z the distance from the fibre, for $z \gg d$. Therefore, the diameter of a spot, or the lateral resolution, at a given distance from the fibre becomes $d_{spot}(z) = 2\sqrt{A/\pi N} \approx \frac{\lambda z}{d}$, or $\sim z/100$ for our system. Our current system manages about half this theoretical resolution, with a spot size of approximately 1 cm diameter at 50cm beyond the fibre.

The initial characterization of the TM is limited in speed by the required camera exposure time, which leads to a typical rate of about 20 patterns per second. The required number of patterns to measure the TM is in the order of 10,000, so this takes in the range of ten minutes. The reconstruction of a set of holograms from the TM corresponding to spots beyond the fibre is limited by computing power, with our current CPU based implementation taking about a minute per pattern. This step can therefore take a full day to form a high-resolution grid of spots.

The speed of the actual imaging once these steps are complete is limited by the repetition rate of the laser, or approximately 7kHz. As every pixel in the image requires at least one pulse, a 30 x 30 pixel image can in principle be recovered at a rate of approximately 7Hz. In practice, however, the signal to noise of such frames is extremely low and several frames need to be averaged to recover a high-quality image. In particular, the results in figure 4 were averaged over 10,000 frames, so took more about 30 minutes to record. For a recognizable but noisy image approximately 10 frames appear to be the minimum.

We have demonstrated a system capable of using time of flight to retrieve 3 dimensional images from up to a meter beyond a multimode fibre using a sub-ns pulsed laser and a transmission matrix measured with a DMD. Images with a lateral resolution of approximately $z/50$ and a lateral resolution of 6cm were recovered from the farfield behind such a fibre.

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7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This is the place to discuss how the approaches above can be transferred to TEM so that their feasibility with electron beams can be tested.

The advantage is however in the large flexibility and in that the results can be perfectly adapted to the specific protein of interest, making it among the most efficient approaches in this context. The drawback at the moment is the sensitivity to both rotation and translation.

- The second implementation requires 3 phase elements but has multiple advantages: - it requires only electrostatic phase elements (therefore it is more dose efficient). – It is insensitive to rotation – It can easily be made protein-specific using tests on many proteins
- The three final sets of implementations require some rethinking in terms of implementation in a TEM. They are not protein-specific so they have an inferior advantage in terms of dose but permit potentially overcoming all problems in the rotation and translation. They require the construction of a specific caustic generator, a set of fiber-like diffusers or, if necessary, an electrostatic aberration tuner. The time of flight of the last approach seems to be an unsurmountable problem at the moment in regular TEMs (but may be approachable in ultrafast transmission electron microscopes []).

With these requirements we think we can proceed primarily in the generation of

- SiN masks for solution 1
- A generalized sorter 3 for solution 2
- A caustic generator or another kind of phase diffuser for the solution 3-5

Further solutions will be evaluated during the rest of the project.

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ANNEX 1:

REFEREE: Stefano Frabboni (University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy)

The deliverable is interesting and full of new and fascinating ideas at the border between optics and electron microscopy. I am here giving my feedback based on my knowledge in the TEM.

In particular I find that the image of the protein in fig 1 should contain a quantitative color scale in order to appreciate what a small phase object means .

We thank the reviewer for the contribution and the kind work. We have indeed modified the image in order for it to be in color and with a color-scale bar.

In section 1 define what is intended by vacuum.

Even if the meaning can appear quite clear, it would be good to rigorously define the vacuum as the plane-wave with unitary intensity as soon as possible in the text.

Done

There is a mixed reference to the small phase approximation in both section 1.1 and section 1.4.

We inserted more cross references between the two sections in order to clarify the topic.

Please explain with better words the feasibility argument in fig 1.4

The argument is somehow inspired by the demonstration of the non-cloning theorem in quantum mechanics. It is not possible to transform a non-orthogonal basis in a basis by unitary transformation.

If two states are non-orthogonal the transformation in another basis of delta will necessarily imply a cross talk.

Please explain with a brief introduction the aim of the solution 1 before entering in detail .

Done

The solution 3-5 are clearly taken from optics but what is the applicability in a TEM ?

The solutions 3 and 4 are explicitly designed for the TEM , in particular solution 4 does not even need a modification of the microscope and can be based on the use of aberration corrector once it is made reliably controlled.

Where do you expect the gain in terms of dose for the method 3,4 come from ?

In general, if the adjustable masks to be used for the corrections are chosen according to our a-priori knowledge of the protein this can be recognized with a limited number of test holograms.

The introduction of the a-priori in the system will be tackled in the future deliverable if this solution is considered in detail.

Q-SORT

Deliverable D.3.1

Manuscript for paper or report on theory advances/test
on diagonalization of operator through coordinate transformation

REFEREE: Ido Kaminer (Technion, Israel)

I think the general topic is very important for future applications of electron microscopy. Developing electron beam shaping/structuring techniques can help improve imaging capabilities in this field in which the resolution and contrast always remain the main challenge. Looking at OAM is good guiding direction, as usual, although generalizing beyond it to more general figure of merits is more important, and indeed becomes the main effort. In the end, all algorithmic-oriented capabilities for electron microscopy that will be using beam shaping will also use more complex structures than only OAM. Still, OAM-carrying beams are good examples of rotation-invariant beam profiles, which is important for certain kinds of target objects.

I think that the promise in this field is amazing, with the results here giving good examples of that. It always feels like it is not moving fast enough, especially when looking for concrete applications in electron microscopy. This is because the technical difficulty is high (especially compared to optics) and the usage of electron microscopes limits how quickly changes can be made.

The text is not fully polished, but it gets the message through.

I think the approaches are interesting – in the direct numerical optimization I was wondering whether there is a plan to apply a convolutional neural network method to optimize the required masks. Like in any other field related to image processing, this will undoubtedly help.

The caustics method is clearly the best developed and best presented. I would place it first. The first approach (chapter 2) is clearly the less developed in terms of presentation. The later methods are presented better and are interesting even if their strength is still on the optics side and not electron microscopy.

We really appreciate the very kind and accurate comments and correction of the referee.

We did our best to polish the text in the limited amount of time we had.

We would like to comment on the final point. It is very difficult for us to judge which solution will be the most promising for the realization for the project. The first approach has the advantage of being direct and scalable to different target proteins. We still think that this method has good possibilities to be implemented in a TEM.

The solution 3 and 4 have good possibility to work in a microscope but the net advantage in terms of dose are still questionable.

Therefore, we ordered the solution from the most to the less relevant to our problem.

As for Convolutional neural network, it seems a very interesting proposal that we will evaluate for the next release of the deliverable.

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ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Multi Modal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL